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Organization and planning of audit of the enterprise of profitability

The subject of research is the peculiarities of the organization and planning of the audit of the profitability of the business entity.

The purpose of the study is to improve planning in order to focus on the most important areas of the audit of profitability, which in turn will identify potential problems, perform work more efficiently and in a short time, properly coordinate the actions of all members of the audit team.

Methodology of work – the study used general and specific methods, such as economic and logical methods and techniques of economic analysis, in particular, graphical and tabular methods.

Results of work: The planning process is defined as the process of developing an overall strategy and approach to the expected nature, timing and scope of the audit. The goals, purpose and objectives of the profitability audit are outlined, the peculiarities of the profitability audit planning process, its stages and implementation procedures are highlighted. The planning process can be divided into three main stages: preliminary planning, preparation of a general audit plan, development of an audit program. The audit program is studied as an important component of the auditor's working documentation, which reflects a significant part of the audit evidence required to confirm the audit opinion. The objectives of the audit program are outlined, such as: a detailed understanding of audit procedures; distribution of responsibilities between members of the working group; establishing a relationship between the various stages of the working group to document the fact of audit procedures. Audit risk has been studied as one that forms an incorrect audit opinion about the financial statements in cases where it contains significant distortions that may affect the decisions of users of financial statements. Assessing the level of auditor's risk is one of the fundamental conditions for effective work, because it determines the time, nature and scope of audit procedures. The stages of assessment of inherent risk in conducting a profitability audit are identified. The objectives of the operation and the structure of the control system of the enterprise, on the basis of which the auditor gets an idea of the state of affairs of the entity. Based on this, a sequence of actions is proposed to assess the risk of controlling the profitability of the enterprise.

Conclusions: the peculiarities of the audit of the profitability of the enterprise in the face of instability are considered. The study suggests a sequence of actions to assess the risk of controlling the profitability of the entity.

Key words: profit, audit organization, audit planning, risk, control, profitability.

КОЦЕРУБА Н.В.

Організація та планування аудиту рентабельності підприємства

Предмет дослідження – особливості організації та планування аудиту рентабельності суб'єкта господарювання.

Мета дослідження – удосконалення планування з метою зосередження на найбільш важливих ділянках аудиту рентабельності, що в свою чергу дасть змогу виявити потенційні проблеми,

виконувати роботу більш ефективно й у стислий термін, правильно скоординувати дії усіх членів аудиторської групи.

Методологія проведення роботи – у дослідженні використовувались загальнонаукові та спеціфічні методи, такі, як економіко–логічні методи та прийоми економічного аналізу, зокрема, графічний та табличний методи.

Результати роботи: Визначено процес планування як процес розробки загальної стратегії і підходу до очікуваного характеру, строків та масштабів аудиторської перевірки. Окреслено цілі, мету та завдання аудиту рентабельності, висвітлено особливості процесу планування аудиту рентабельності, його стадії та процедури здійснення. Процес планування можна поділити на три основні стадії: попереднє планування, складання загального плану аудиту, розробка програми аудиту. Досліджено програму аудиту, як важливу складову робочої документації аудитора, що відображає значну частину аудиторських доказів, потрібних для підтвердження аудиторської думки. Окреслено цілі програми аудиту, такі, як: детальне уявлення про аудиторських процедур; розподіл відповідальності між членами робочої групи; встановлення взаємозв'язку між різними етапами робочої групи задокументування факту виконання аудиторських процедур. Досліджено аудиторський ризик, як такий що формує неправильну аудиторську думку про фінансову звітність у тих випадках, коли вона містить суттєві викривлення, які можуть вплинути на рішення користувачів фінансової звітності. Оцінка рівня ризику аудитора є однією з основоположних умов ефективної роботи, оскільки, на її основі визначають час, характер та обсяг аудиторських процедур. Виокремлено етапи оцінки властивого ризику при проведенні аудиту рентабельності. Досліджено цілі функціонування та структуру системи контролю підприємства, на основі якої аудитор отримує уявлення про стан справ суб'єкта господарювання. На основі цього запропоновано послідовність дій для оцінки ризику контролю рентабельності підприємства.

Висновки: розглянуто особливості здійснення аудиту рентабельності підприємства в умовах нестабільності. За результатами дослідження запропоновано послідовність дій для оцінки ризику контролю рентабельності суб'єкта господарювання.

Ключові слова: прибуток, організація аудиту, планування аудиту, ризик, контроль, рентабельність.
КОЦЕРУБА Н.В.

Организация и планирование аудита рентабельности предприятия

Предмет исследования – особенности организации и планирования аудита рентабельности предприятия.

Цель исследования – совершенствование планирования с целью сосредоточения на наиболее важных участках аудита рентабельности, что в свою очередь позволит выявить потенциальные проблемы, выполнять работу более эффективно и в сжатые сроки, правильно скоординировать действия всех членов аудиторской группы.

Методология проведения работы – в исследовании использовались общенаучные и специфические методы, такие, как экономико–логические методы и приемы экономического анализа, в частности, графический и табличный методы.

Результаты работы: Определен процесс планирования как процесс разработки общей стратегии и подхода к ожидаемому характеру, срокам и масштабам аудиторской проверки. Определены цели, цели и задачи аудита рентабельности, освещены особенности процесса планирования аудита рентабельности, его стадии и процедуры осуществления. Процесс планирования можно разделить на три основные стадии: предварительное планирование, составление общего плана аудита, разработка программы аудита. Исследовано программу аудита, как важную составляющую рабочей документации аудитора, отражающий значительную часть аудиторских доказательств, необходимых для подтверждения аудиторского мнения. Определены цели программы аудита, такие, как: детальное представление об аудиторских процедурах; распределение ответственности между членами рабочей группы; установление взаимосвязи между различными эта-

пами рабочей группы по документированию факта выполнения аудиторских процедур. Исследован аудиторский риск, как таковой формирует неправильное аудиторское мнение о финансовой отчетности в тех случаях, когда она содержит существенные искажения, которые могут повлиять на решение пользователей финансовой отчетности. Оценка уровня риска аудитора является одной из основных условий эффективной работы, поскольку, по ее основе определяют время, характер и объем аудиторских процедур. Выделены этапы оценки неотъемлемого риска при проведении аудита рентабельности. Исследованы цели функционирования и структуру системы контроля предприятия, на основе которой аудитор получает представление о состоянии дел предприятия. На основе этого предложено последовательность действий для оценки риска контроля рентабельности предприятия.

Выводы: рассмотрены особенности осуществления аудита рентабельности предприятия в условиях нестабильности. По результатам исследования предложено последовательность действий для оценки риска контроля рентабельности предприятия.

Ключевые слова: прибыль, организация аудита, планирования аудита, риск, контроль, рентабельность.

Formulation of the problem. An effective audit of the company's profitability is possible only if the planning process is properly organized. Planning is the development of an overall strategy and a detailed approach to the expected nature, timing and scope of the audit. Proper planning allows you to focus on the most important areas of the profitability audit, which in turn allows you to identify potential problems, perform work more efficiently and in a short time, to properly coordinate the actions of all members of the audit team.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The organization and planning of the audit of the profitability of the enterprise was studied in the works of a number of modern domestic authors, such as: Goraetsky R., Golovchenko T., Zemskaya G., Nesterenko A., Tsal-Tsalko Y., Yanushkevich I. In these studies, the list of audit procedures and sources is not clearly defined, and accordingly there is a duplication of accounting stages of the subject technology. The audit actions and components that should be specified in the auditing standards have not been studied. Also, the issues of efficiency theory remain insufficiently defined, hence the cost audit and the generalized characteristics of the quality of the profitability audit. It is because of risk reduction that these methods of determining the effectiveness of a profitability audit are limited to assessing the effectiveness of the audit. Today, the main unresolved issue in enterprise profit management is the development of tools and procedures for comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of the profitability audit.

Unresolved parts of the problem: today there are a number of unresolved issues regarding the orga-

nization and planning of the audit of the profitability of the enterprise in modern business conditions. Need a detailed study of the planning and implementation of audit procedures for the profitability of the enterprise in conditions of instability.

The purpose of the study is: to study the features of the organization and planning of the audit of the profitability of the business entity; coverage of the purpose, goals, principles and objectives of the profitability audit; outlining the features of the audit program on the topic of the study; study of potential risks of auditing the profitability of the enterprise.

Presentation of the main research material: Planning means developing an overall strategy and approach to the expected nature, timing and extent of the audit.

The purpose of this process is:

- development of a general audit plan with the definition of the expected scope, schedules and timing of the audit;

- preparation of the audit program with the establishment of the scope, types and sequence of audit procedures sufficient for the collection of audit evidence and the formation of a reasonable opinion on the reliability of the financial statements of the enterprise.

Thus, planning is the definition of the means to achieve the audit objective and aims to:

- audit strategy development is a set of many decisions made by the auditor from the moment of work planning to its completion;

- assistance in the management and control of the work of auditors;

- providing the necessary attention to important aspects of the audit;

Fig. 1. The main shortcomings that arise in the process of planning a profitability audit

- the most effective disposal of available staff;
- ensuring the effective execution of works.

The goals and objectives of the audit detail its purpose, which is to express an independent qualified opinion on the reliability of financial statements, which prevents the main shortcomings that arise in the planning process (Fig. 1).

It is important for the auditor to have the necessary understanding. Gaining insight is a continuous process of collecting, updating and analyzing information during an audit, which begins at the planning stage and upon completion of the audit allows you to formulate an information base for subsequent audits.

Conventionally, the whole planning process can be divided into three main stages: preliminary planning, preparation of a general audit plan, development of an audit program.

The general plan is a list of works at the main stages of the audit, which is a guide in the implementation of the program. The development of a general plan involves the mandatory determination of audit risk and level of materiality, which allows you to determine the necessary audit procedures (scope of procedures), the method of audit (continuous, selective), to form a group of auditors. The content of the plan should take into account the requirements of auditing standards and include:

- knowledge of the client's business;
- understanding of accounting and internal control systems;
- risk and materiality assessment;
- determining the nature, timing and scope of procedures;
- coordination, analysis and control of work performed;
- other aspects.

The auditor may discuss certain elements of the general plan and individual audit procedures with

the head of the audit firm, management and personnel of the economic entity in order to increase the effectiveness of the audit and coordination of audit procedures with the work of personnel of the economic entity. However, the responsibility for developing the overall plan rests with the auditor [1, p. 201].

The general plan is submitted for consideration and approval to the head of the audit firm. If there are doubts about the effectiveness and feasibility of individual procedures, then develop several versions of the plan (the whole plan, or its individual sections). After their consideration, one of the options is approved by the head.

Although the documentation of the overall audit plan should be sufficiently detailed to serve as a guide in developing the audit program. The form and content of the plan will change depending on the size of the economic entity, the degree of complexity of the audit, as well as specific methods and technologies used by the auditor [4, p. 243]. The following audit procedures are typical for planning:

- consideration of the client's business background and an attempt to identify any problems that exist in this sector of the economy that may affect the work of the auditor;
- drawing up an audit plan, taking into account the extent to which internal control can be relied upon and the extent to which work can be divided into intermediate and final stages of the auditor;
- consideration of problems that arose during the audit of the previous year, by checking the files and discussing them with the staff who participated in the previous audit in order to identify facts that may relate to the audit of the current year;
- assessment of the impact of any changes in legislation or accounting practice on the client's financial statements;

- consideration of any management reports or other reports prepared by the client, as they may indicate areas for attention to the auditor;
- meetings with senior management of the client to identify problematic issues;
- allocation of time to important stages of preparation of financial statements, such as the date of the inventory, audit of accounting records, receivables and payables, preparation of the trial balance sheet and draft report;
- determining the degree of ability of the client's staff to analyze and summarize financial data, the adequacy of the work performed by internal auditors;
- determining the need to involve experts and other auditors in the audit;
- determining the number and qualifications of auditors at each stage of the audit;
- holding consultations with members of the audit team, discussing with them problems that can be foreseen in advance;
- calculation of the time budget, which should be carried out on the basis of time allocation (level of qualification) of each member of the audit team.
- informing the client about the expected dates of the audit staff's visit and the agreements reached.

The next stage of the planning process is the development of an audit program. The audit program, which is a tool for implementing the plan, is both an instruction for audit assistants and a means of quality control of all members of the audit team, as it has a detailed description of the essence of audit procedures.

The main objectives of the audit program:

- provide a detailed view of the audit procedures required to perform the task;
- distribution of responsibilities between members of the working group;
- establishing the relationship between the various stages of the working group to document the fact of audit procedures.

During the preparation of the program, the auditor should take into account: certain assessments of inherent risk and control risk, the level of confidence to be provided in substantive inspections, the timing of control tests and substantive verification procedures, coordination of any assistance to be received from the client, the presence of assistants, the involvement of other auditors or experts [2, p.96].

Each audit procedure must have a number and code in order for the auditor to be able to mark them in his or her working papers.

The audit program is an important component of the auditor's working documentation that reflects a significant portion of the audit evidence required to support the auditor's opinion. The program is a table that contains audit procedures required to perform. Procedures or tests can be recorded under headings that reflect management's assertions about financial statements (objectives) and tests for any area of audit. Thus, under a certain number (code) indicate the statement (purpose) «Rights and obligations», and then list under the appropriate serial numbers (codes) audit procedures aimed at verifying compliance or non-compliance with this statement (or achievement or failure to achieve this goal) .

The audit program may also be in the form of a program of control tests and tests (procedures) on the merits. The control test program is a set of actions aimed at collecting information about the effectiveness of the internal control system of the client. The test program is essentially a detailed check of the correctness of the reflection in the accounting of turnover and account balances, ie a list of actions for detailed specific checks. In this case, the auditor determines the specific areas of audit (accounting sections), which he will check and compile a program for each of them.

Documented conclusions are formed from each section of the program, which are the basis for the formation and expression of the auditor's opinion in the audit report and conclusion.

The audit program, as well as the general plan, should be reviewed during the audit (if necessary). The reasons for all changes must be documented.

During the audit, the auditor is responsible for his opinion on the client's financial statements. The report is based on the auditor's professional judgment regarding the evidence obtained during the audit. Therefore, the auditor should be careful in gathering evidence (that is, the auditor should plan his or her work so that all material aspects that may affect the decisions of users of the financial statements are examined), and in evaluating the evidence, it should be objective. The risk that the auditor will form an incorrect opinion about the financial statements in cases where it contains significant distortions that may affect the decisions of users of financial statements, is called audit risk [3, p.163].

The auditor's risk assessment is one of the fundamental conditions for effective work. Based on it,

the time, nature and scope of audit procedures are determined.

Audit risk is determined by the formula:

$$AR = IR * CR * DR \quad (1)$$

IR – internal (inherent) risk;

CR – control risk;

DR – risk of non-detection.

The assessment of inherent risk is carried out at the planning stage. As this risk arises in the presence of conditions that are not related to the control system in the enterprise, its assessment is always approximate and subjective, so it is necessary to follow the sequence of actions to assess the inherent risk (Table 1).

The first step determines the owners, their characteristics, assessment of the equity structure. Analysis of the owners of a controlling stake or significant owners (whose share in the authorized capital is more than 20%) to assess their possible impact on the activities of the enterprise. This will identify those owners who may later act as partners, which requires an assessment of the correctness of the transactions (payments to third parties, related parties, etc.). These factors increase the inherent risk.

In the second step, the inherent risk will be high – if the industry is developing or in crisis, the client’s business is irregular (seasonal), the presence of a wide network of branches and subsidiaries located in different regions or countries with different economies. Risk assessment at this stage is based on the reality of the assumption of business continuity, taking into account all factors. If there is significant uncertainty, the risk is considered high.

In the third step, the inherent risk will be high if the company is large in size and has a complex horizontal and vertical structure (ie there is a risk that the auditor will not be able to identify and verify all significant chains in the cash flows of the company). Risk assessment is based on the calculation of the time allotted for the audit and the volume of activity of the enterprise.

In the fourth step, conducting analytical procedures to determine changes in the enterprise, consistency in the activities of the enterprise with other similar enterprises in these industries, identifying unusual trends or changes in accounts. If there are significant inconsistencies and unusual trends in the financial statements, the inherent risk is previously considered high.

The fifth step is to identify the main partners. The presence of one or two major partners increases the auditor’s uncertainty about future events, especially in the presence of significant debts. This increases the inherent risk. To assess the risk, it is necessary to obtain information about the financial condition of these partners and determine the degree of their interest in the auditor’s client.

In the sixth step, all factors are multiplied if they are expressed as a percentage. When qualitatively characterizing the factors, it is advisable to use a risk assessment matrix.

The next component of the audit risk module is control risk. From the point of view of the independent auditor, the assessment of control risk, as well as inherent risk, is carried out in several stages (Table 2).

At the stage of acquaintance with the control system the auditor gets an idea of its purpose, functioning and structure, which consists of the following elements:

- control environment, ie conditions for control (including the process of risk assessment of the sub-farm);
- information systems related to financial reporting (accounting system);
- control procedures.

Control tests are performed to obtain audit evidence about the proper organization and effectiveness of accounting and internal control systems over a period of time. When testing the means of control, auditors are interested not so much in finding specific errors and distortions, but in iden-

Table 1. Stages of assessment of inherent risk in the audit of profitability

Sequence stage	Sequence of stages of inherent risk assessment
1	Acquaintance with constituent documents
2	Collection of data on the activities of the business entity and industry
3	Assessment of the structure of the enterprise
4	Analysis of financial documentation for the last years of activity
5	Analysis of activity partners
6	Final and preliminary assessment of inherent risk

tifying the shortcomings of accounting and control systems, which are aimed at preventing errors, their timely detection and correction.

The next step after getting acquainted with the accounting and control system is a preliminary assessment of the amount of control risk.

Control tests are performed to obtain audit evidence about the proper organization and effectiveness of accounting and internal control systems over a period of time. When testing the means of control, auditors are interested not so much in finding specific errors and distortions, but in identifying the shortcomings of accounting and control systems, which are aimed at preventing errors, their timely detection and correction.

Tests of the control system may consist of the following procedures:

- checking records or documents confirming transactions and other events in order to obtain audit evidence of the proper use of internal control, for example, checking the permission of the head to carry out operations;
- requests and observations and the use of internal controls that do not leave documentary evidence for the audit, such as determining the actual rather than the nominal performer of each function;
- re-execution of procedures or control measures to ensure that these actions were performed correctly by the entity, for example, re-execution of the classification of receivables by maturity.

Preliminary risk assessment of controls is the process of determining the effectiveness of the client's accounting and internal control systems in terms of preventing or detecting and correcting material misstatements. There is always some control risk due to the limitations inherent in any accounting and internal control system.

Non-detection risk assessment is performed similarly to other components of audit risk: preliminary risk assessment, its clarification during testing, the final assessment of the amount of risk. If we take the

inherent risk as a constant value, the risk of non-detection can be calculated inversely depending on the size of the control risk. That is, the higher the control risk, the lower the detection risk should be, which is achieved by increasing the volume of tests in fact. The risks of non-disclosure depend on the professionalism of the auditor and determine the amount of audit evidence that the auditor plans to gather to obtain an opinion on the financial statements. Thus, the probability of not detecting errors, fraud and other irregularities affects the entire work of the auditor, in particular, the choice of methods, techniques and procedures of verification to be applied to the sample, the criteria for assessing financial risks.

Conclusions

Thus, the peculiarities of the audit of the profitability of the enterprise are considered, namely: the goals, purpose and its tasks are outlined; features of the planning process, its stages and implementation procedures are highlighted; the profitability audit program is investigated; the potential audit risk of inaccurate assessment of financial statements is analyzed. The stages of assessment of inherent risk in conducting a profitability audit are identified. The objectives of the operation and structure of the control system of the enterprise, on the basis of which the auditor gets an idea of the state of affairs of the entity. The study suggests a sequence of actions to assess the risk of controlling the profitability of the entity.

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Table 2. The sequence of actions to assess the risk of profitability control

Sequence stage	The sequence of stages of risk assessment of profitability control
1	acquaintance with the system of internal control and accounting
2	preliminary risk assessment of control
3	determining the need for tests of control moments (compliance tests)
4	testing of the control system, if such a need exists
5	clarification of the amount of control risk in accordance with the test results
6	use these results to choose one of two options: additional testing of control, or planning (expansion) of tests on the merits

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Класифікація факторів впливу на збут продукції

Предметом дослідження є класифікація факторів впливу на збут продукції у сучасних умовах господарювання.

Мета дослідження – визначити фактори впливу на збут продукції.

Методи дослідження. У роботі використані діалектичний метод наукового пізнання, метод аналізу і синтезу, порівняльний метод, метод узагальнення даних.

Результати роботи. У статті наведена класифікація факторів впливу на збут продукції у сучасних умовах господарювання. Розглянуто фактори впливу на збут продукції відповідно до умов конкретного суб'єкта національного господарства, зокрема: ціна продукції, якість продукції, логістика поставок, гарантійне та післягарантійне обслуговування, імідж підприємства, вплив конкуренції, реклама, умови оплати, інноваційна діяльність, інвестиційна діяльність, регулювання експорту й імпорту продукції.

Висновки. Результатами проведеного дослідження стали наступні висновки. Узагальнено і доповнено існуючі класифікації факторів впливу на збут продукції. Запропонована класифікація дозволяє ґрунтовніше підібрати систему факторів відповідно до умов конкретного суб'єкта національного господарства, що є підставою для його успішного функціонування.

Ключові слова: підприємство, конкурентоспроможність, торгівля, ринок, продукція, збут, покупець, ефективність.

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Классификация факторов влияния на сбыт продукции

Предметом исследования является классификация факторов влияния на сбыт продукции в